

Marketing Research in Project Ukrainian Studies Platform (Demobilized Soldiers of the Ato Area) - The Educational Action Plan "A Step to Entrepreneurship"

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ABSTRACT

Marketing research is the solution to any marketing problem (advertising effectiveness research, pricing strategy research, etc.). The purpose of these studies is to identify qualitative changes. The key to marketing research is to provide the information you need to make marketing decisions. The content of marketing research can be defined in several aspects: as a business process, as a whole in the knowledge of marketing research as a source of methods and tools.

Keywords: marketing, marketing research, marketing research process

1. INTRODUCTION

Marketing is a system that includes a wealth of knowledge and requires a lot of new and relevant information to properly manage this system and achieve its goals. The aim of marketing research is to organize and carry out the collection, analysis and presentation of information on the marketing problem. When the marketing information is properly managed, it can accurately identify the strengths and weaknesses of the companies, find out expansion opportunities and threats of failure, and identify the appropriate ways of operating an external marketing environment. Marketing research is the solution to any marketing problem. Advertising effectiveness research, pricing strategy research and others are conducted. Marketing research is done to collect the necessary information to allow you to make marketing decisions. Companies need to be able to manage large-scale commercial information, understand and analyze market processes in order to stay competitive on the market and continue to operate successfully. Almost all companies are constantly looking for information about what a person wants and why. It all depends on the buyer. Therefore, the purpose of marketing research is to provide information of a kind that will help make informed decisions. Marketing research also needed in the project Ukrainian studies platform (demobilized soldiers of the ato area) - the educational action plan "a step to entrepreneurship because demobilized soldiers wants to create their own business, to be entrepreneur.

2. Definition marketing research

The purpose of market research is to avoid the misuse of business resources and to accurately assess the nature and level of demand for products and services. Market research seeks to clarify current and future market demands. Market research helps to plan much ahead. In addition, the most up-to-date information is needed to make the right decisions and meet consumer expectations.

Market Research Tasks:

Provide information that will allow the manufacturer to design a product that meets the needs of customers.
Find out how much to buy products to be redeemed.
Explain how to deliver a product to fit an effective advertising and distribution process.

Types of market research:

Distribution research.

These studies help answer the questions:

Why the product is not fast enough;

Why distributors are reluctant to distribute it;

What is the popularity of competing products;

What are the stocks of each type of product;

Which channels are the goods provided?

These studies should be carried out continuously.

Consumer research These tests may be permanent or for a specific purpose. When research is conducted for a specific purpose, the questionnaire is made on the most important points in trying to find out:

Which group of people are buying one or another product?

What sex/

What age/

How often?

How much?

When research is carried out continuously, it seeks to measure changes in demand for goods. It provides information about the wishes of customers, how much to produce products and how to make products suitable for effective advertising.

Product research. These tests are designed to find out how the buyer is adopting a new product. If the product is no longer new, then these studies can clarify the characteristics of the products already on the market if they are sold less than expected. These studies are carried out according to the following principle: the study participant is given access to various types of products. Although they look the same, they are specially labeled. Subsequent reports are analyzed and prepared to help you make the right conclusions.

Advertising research. These studies are very broad and diverse in shape. They cover all the media used for advertising and help you to understand the influence of advertising.

Motivational research. These studies are part of consumer research. They explain why people buy one instead of buying another.

Thus, the information obtained from market research helps to design products, their price and advertising. Market

research information is very important for advertising. It is from this information that we create promotional texts that tell us why people buy products and so on. In the past, advertising was based on intuition and guesswork, market research today helps to select effective advertising.

Table1. Marketing reserach definition

Author	Definition
Hague, P. (2006)	„Market researchers do not just poke around in a market to see what is going on. They have research designs and plans. They are therefore systematic in what they do. Furthermore, they seek to uncover the truth which may be hidden under a pile of assumptions or bias. It is the researcher’s task to be objective.“
Al-Shatanawi, H., A, Osman, O., Ab Halim, M., S.	„Market research is a process of gathering, analyzing and interpreting information about a market, about a product or service to be offered for sale in that market, and about the past, present and potential customers for the product or service; research into the characteristics, spending habits, location and needs of your business’s target market, the industry as a whole, and the particular competitors you face“ (Gupta & Benedett & 2007).
Smith, S., M., Albaum, G., S. (2013)	Marketing success is measured by new product ratings, increased brand awareness, brand likeability ratings, uniqueness, purchase intent, and customer satisfaction. In measuring each of these constructs, we often refer to models.
Waller, L. (2013)	Market Research is defined systematic design, collection, analysis and reporting of data and findings relevant to a specific marketing situation. It can help companies to determine whether the product or service will satisfy customers' needs. Market research can identify market trends, demographics, economic shifts, customer's buying habits, and important information on competition. Market research is essential for the survival and growth of your business.
Baldwin, P. (2007)	Market research is the systematic and objective identification, collection, analysis and reporting of information for the purpose of assisting organisations in decisions relating to the understanding of the behaviours and attitudes of people and their organisations, the ultimate aim being the development and implementation of solutions to problems or opportunities.
Miller, T. W. (2000)	We might expect many marketing research firms to stop growing, not because the need for business or consumer information declines, but because those firms think of themselves as being in the marketing research industry rather than in the information industry. What
Polaris Marketing Research (2012)	The marketing research process includes the systematic identification, collection, analysis and distribution of information for the purpose of knowledge development and decision making. The reasons and times at which your company or organization might consider performing marketing research varies, but the general purpose of gaining intelligence for decision making remains constant throughout.
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3. Marketing research process

The purpose of marketing research is to improve management decisions, their content, quality, and increase their reliability. To achieve this, quality, reliable and accurate information is needed. When making marketing decisions, information comes from:

- personal experience;
- communication with executives, company employees;
- financial documents;
- competitive environment;
- marketing research.

Marketing research is the objective and systematic collection of information, its analysis and use, and the solution to the marketing problem.

Objective information collection means that it is not influenced by subjective opinions.

The systematic collection of information is planned at all stages.

Based on marketing research, information can be collected about:

- Organizational macro-environment (socio-cultural, economic, technological, political-legal environment);
- Company micro-environment (suppliers, intermediaries, competitors, partners);
- Elements of the marketing complex (product, price, distribution, sponsorship);

- Consumers (consumer opinion, image, demand, needs, lifestyle, demographic data, social dependency).

Marketing research includes the following steps:

1. Research problem / goal clarification / definition, the most important and most difficult stage of marketing research process. At this stage you need to answer the questions:

What is the problem?

What do I need to know?

What is the real reason for the problem / (ys)?

What are the research goals?

It is necessary to not confuse the symptoms with the real problem. A good problem definition / definition allows you to:

- avoid unnecessary collection of information;
- collecting enough information to analyze the problem;
- allocate resources correctly.

2. Preparation of the research plan. At this stage you need to answer the questions:

What information do we need? Accumulated information must:

- meet the objectives of the study;
- resolve the problem to be solved.

What are the possible sources of information? The sources of information may include:

- secondary data;
- Initial data.

The first is to analyze which questions of the problem can be answered using secondary data, but secondary data has a number of drawbacks:

- It is often not possible to verify the accuracy of the data;
- may be inaccurate, outdated;
- may be presented in an unacceptable form;
- may be incomplete;
- may be over / under-generalized;
- may not have the necessary information.

3. Data collection and analysis. At this stage, the following works are being carried out: a decision is taken on who will collect the data: whether the organization is on its own or will be hired by a subcontractor; data collection is carried out; Collected data is grouped, structured, and analyzed so that it is appropriate to find answers to the marketing questions raised.

4. Preparation of the study report, which contains:

- Research results;
- Interpretation of results;
- Conclusions are made;
- The recommendations are provided.

In summary, marketing research is the search, accumulation, analysis of the information needed for marketing decisions, which is used in the market analysis of the company's external and internal environment, SWOT. In the market analysis, the most commonly used marketing method, such as segmentation.

Figure1. Marketing research process steps (Kraučionienė (2005))

Segmentation is a marketing method that divides a company into separate segments of the specific characteristics (consumers, products, territories, product demand, customers, carriers), taking into account the results of market analysis. The market segments are consumers who react equally to the company's actions, demand formation and sales promotion.

The main purpose of market research is to obtain systematic data on competitors, products, prices, market share, macro-factors and their trends. In order to prepare a reasonable and effective marketing plan, periodic market research is required, i.e. y analysis of external factors influencing the company's activities. The company's marketing department initiates market research, formulates research objectives. A market research firm can do its part to include employees of other departments who, in their daily routine, receive the market information they need, or can use the services of a market research agency (a subcontractor is used).

The marketing department prepares a market research plan - a proposal and an estimate, chooses a subcontractor for market research (selection criteria: long experience of cooperation, positive feedback and recommendations, valid ISO 9001 certificate for products or services ordered, the optimal combination of quality and price, etc.) It is decided to conduct market research by the company, the marketing department makes a research plan, prepares data registration templates and methodologies, which should include the scope of research, data and information gathering methods, tools, research objects, identify competitors, select the methods used by the secret buyer to assign tasks to marketing managers. and other The department heads conduct market research, control and coordinate their progress. Market research can be done by the company to include employees of other departments who, in their daily routine, receive the market information they need, or can use the services of a market research agency (subcontractor). The marketing department prepares a market research plan - a proposal and an estimate, chooses a subcontractor for market research (selection criteria: long experience of cooperation, positive feedback and recommendations, valid ISO 9001 certificate for products or services ordered, the optimal combination of quality and price, etc.) It is decided to conduct market research by the company, the marketing department makes a research plan, prepares data registration templates and methodologies, which should include the scope of research, data and information gathering methods, tools, research objects, identify competitors, select the methods used by the secret buyer to assign tasks to marketing managers. and other

department heads to conduct market research, control and coordinate their progress. The marketing department analyzes, aggregates the results, gives conclusions and recommendations.

Conclusions

Market research will reveal the real market situation, redeem unused business opportunities, evaluate the benefits of yours and your competitors, and present a precise portrait of your existing or potential users. In order to avoid misuse of business resources, it is necessary to accurately assess the nature and level of demand for products and services. Market research is aimed at ascertaining the current and future market requirements as accurately as possible. More sophisticated production technologies require higher capital investment, and planning is far ahead. People's income has grown, and this affects consumer demands, so the most up-to-date information is needed to make the right decisions. Ideally, market research should provide information that would allow the manufacturer to design a product that meets the customers' wishes, to produce it so that it is redeemed, packaged in a manner that is suitable for an effective advertising and distribution process.

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